

Correlation of the Testicular Sonographic Biometric Features and Semen Quality as Tools in Breeding Soundness Examination of Red Sokoto Bucks

Adamu, U.¹ and Ibrahim, B.¹

¹Department of Theriogenology and Animal Production, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.

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Breeding soundness evaluation (BSE) is a vital component in the selection of fertile sires for livestock production, particularly among indigenous breeds such as the Red Sokoto goat (RSG) buck. This study aimed to investigate the correlation between testicular sonographic biometric features and semen quality as tools for evaluating breeding soundness in Red Sokoto bucks. Sixty mature Red Sokoto bucks in Sokoto, Nigeria, were subjected to detailed semen analysis and ultrasonographic evaluation of testicular dimensions. Semen parameters assessed included volume, progressive motility, live ratio, morphology, pH, and sperm concentration. Sonographic measurements included testicular length, height, width, and volume, with echotexture also examined. Mean semen volume was 0.85 ± 0.299 ml, progressive motility $77.33 \pm 14.305\%$, live spermatozoa $89.18 \pm 9.118\%$, and sperm morphology $80.07 \pm 7.481\%$. Sperm concentration was $374 \pm 138.923 \times 10^9/\text{ml}$. Testicular volumes were larger on the right side ($115.23 \pm 25.264 \text{ cm}^3$) than the left ($89.95 \pm 18.280 \text{ cm}^3$), with uniform hypoechoic echotexture and scattered hyperechoic spots. A positive correlation was observed between testicular volume and sperm concentration. The combination of ultrasonographic testicular measurements and semen quality parameters provides a reliable approach to breeding soundness examination in Red Sokoto bucks. Testicular volume and echotexture are valuable predictors of semen quality, and their evaluation should be considered a standard tool in reproductive soundness assessment for breeding selection in small ruminants.

Keywords: Red Sokoto buck, breeding soundness evaluation (BSE), ultrasonography, semen quality, testicular biometrics, reproductive evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

The Red Sokoto goat is a small ruminant with significant breeding potential, making it a valuable source of animal protein through meat and milk production (Devendra, 1999). To maximize the production capabilities of these goats, especially in breeding programs, a thorough breeding soundness examination (BSE) is crucial. This is particularly vital in male goats, as one buck can breed multiple does, and this ratio is even higher in assisted reproductive techniques such as artificial insemination

(Ajala et al., 2013).

Breeding soundness examination (BSE) has become an essential practice in assessing male fertility across various livestock species (Brito et al., 2004). The goal of BSE is to evaluate a male's ability to impregnate a specific number of females within a defined period. While Red Sokoto goats are known to breed year-round, their fertility characteristics are not well-documented, impeding effective genetic improvement through selective breeding and crossbreeding. Essential biometric parameters, such as scrotal circumference (SC), testicular weight (TW), testicular volume (TV), and testicular length (TL), are key indicators in the andrological evaluation of male goats.

*Corresponding author's e-mail: edzu1973@gmail.com.

A comprehensive BSE, which includes an evaluation of semen quality, is necessary to determine the reproductive capacity of a buck (Ohashi et al., 2007). Semen analysis is crucial for assessing the fertility potential of bucks, as it provides insights into sperm concentration, motility, morphology, and viability—parameters that are fundamental to predicting fertility (Zahner et al., 2011; Sousa et al., 2010). During the BSE, particular attention is given to the testes, as they are responsible for the production of sperm cells and testosterone, both of which are vital for fertilization and the expression of sexual characteristics necessary for efficient reproduction (Daramola et al., 2006; Udeh and Oghenesode, 2011).

While testicular palpation is often part of routine BSE, it is difficult to assess the internal condition of the testes using this method. This limitation can lead to challenges in diagnosing normal and abnormal testicular conditions. Testicular ultrasound, or sonography, offers a non-invasive, painless solution to this issue. Using reflected sound waves, ultrasound generates detailed images of the testes, epididymis, and scrotum. Unlike X-rays, ultrasound does not involve ionizing radiation and has no reported side effects. The technique involves sending sound waves through testicular tissues via a transducer, with structures being classified as echogenic (reflective) or anechoic (non-reflective). This allows for a detailed examination of both normal and abnormal conditions of the testes and associated structures (Dina and Higgins, 2002).

Research on testicular ultrasound has been conducted in various animals, including cattle (Yimer et al., 2008), camels (Pasha et al., 2011), sheep (Andrade et al., 2014), Alpine goats (Carazo et al., 2014), and dogs (Camara et al., 2014). However, there is a notable lack of studies on the use of testicular ultrasound for Red Sokoto bucks, particularly in relation to biometric parameters like testicular width, height, and volume, which are essential indicators of fertility.

The reproductive performance of Red Sokoto bucks remains suboptimal, largely due to the absence of effective and accurate fertility evaluation techniques. Traditional methods, such as physical examinations alone, often fail to provide comprehensive and reliable assessments of fertility. More advanced evaluation techniques are needed to improve breeding soundness evaluations (Ming et al., 2021). Furthermore, there is a gap in knowledge regarding the correlation between testicular ultrasonography and semen quality in Red Sokoto bucks (Mariana da Silva Ribeiro et al., 2017).

This study aims to investigate the correlation between ultrasonographic biometric evaluations of the testes and semen quality in Red Sokoto bucks, with the goal of improving breeding soundness evaluation practices. A breeding soundness examination (BSE) systematically evaluates a buck's reproductive health, anatomy, and physiology to assess its suitability for breeding (Holtz,

2000).

The primary objective of BSE is to identify potential reproductive issues or abnormalities that may impact the buck's fertility and breeding performance. Conducting BSEs prior to each breeding season ensures that only reproductively sound bucks are used for mating, thereby maximizing breeding success and herd productivity (Sousa et al., 2010). By combining testicular sonography with semen quality analysis, this study seeks to provide a more accurate, reliable tool for evaluating fertility in Red Sokoto bucks, ultimately contributing to improved breeding outcomes and herd management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The study was conducted in Department of Theriogenology and animal production, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Sokoto state, which is located in the extreme Northwestern part of Nigeria. The state geographically lies along longitude 11° 30' to 13° 50' East and latitudes 4° to 6' North and covers a total land mass of 26,648.48 square kilometers.

Experimental animals and management

A total of Sixty (60) matured apparently healthy Red Sokoto Bucks of proven reproductive capability were selected for this study, aged 1–2 years, weighing between 20 and 35 kg. They were fed on commercial ruminant feed and water provided ad libitum.

Semen Collection

Semen samples were collected from all the sixty (60) selected bucks by using the electro-ejaculation method (Bailey® Ejaculator) once. Briefly, the preputial hairs of the bucks were clipped using a sharp sterile scissors and then cleaned gently with tissue paper. K-Y jelly (lubricant) was applied on the probe of the battery operated electro-ejaculator. The bucks were then restrained by two attendants and the hind limbs were elevated from the ground at an angle of 45° and the lubricated probe was then inserted gently into the rectum to a depth of 10–12 cm on the floor of the pelvis, touching the mucous membrane at the position of the ampulla.

The ampulla stimulation was done by alternately increasing and decreasing the voltage time until full erection and ejaculation were achieved then collected into a clean warm graduated semen collection vial through a funnel with a handle brought over the glans penis around the preputial area. Immediately after collection, the test tube was removed and placed into a water bath maintained at 37°C, and transported to the AI laboratory for macroscopic and microscopic analyses.

Figure 1: Ultrasound machine (iScan 2 MULTI)

The red arrow indicating control buttons, white arrow showing calibration, Light green indicating cylindrical probe, blue arrow showing the screen (monitor) and the orange colored arrow indicating the concave probe of the mobile ultrasound machine respectively

Testicular Ultrasound and Biometrics

The mobile ultrasound machine (Iscan 2 Multi Draminski) was used for this study, each of the buck were properly restrained by an assistant holding the animal firmly with the two limbs separated such that the testes were freely hanging caudally and at a distance of about 10 cm away from the ultrasound machine (UM). The testes were thoroughly cleaned with cotton wool soaked in methylated alcohol before ultrasound gel (UG) was applied generously covering the entire testicular surface. The testes of the Red Sokoto buck is only covered by a thin layer of hair, hence there was no need for shaving (Raji et al. 2021). The ultrasound machine was connected to a stabilizer which has fixed in-bulld light source. The convex shaped transducer was then connected carefully to the monitor and switched on to the real time single B – mode at a frequency of 7.5 MHz. The ultrasound gel was also applied on the probe covering the entire surface and then pressed gently on the surface of the testes. The images produced on the monitor were frozen and stored on the ultrasound machine. Testicular ultrasound protocol for the bucks involved viewing the transverse plane (TP) for both testes, the right testis and the left testis; and then on the longitudinal planes (LP) for the right testis and the left testis. The testicular parameters measured were: width of both testes which was taken on the transverse plane for both testes. This

was measured from the most lateral point of the right testis to the most lateral point of the left testis using the electronic caliper. The length of the testis (L) was taken on the longitudinal planes and was measured from the most cranial point on the testis to the most caudal point of the testes using the electronic caliper. The height of the testis (H) was measured by placing the electronic caliper from the highest ventral to the lowest dorsal points of the testes on the LP. The width (W) was measured as the widest diameter between the lateral and medial aspects of the testes on the TP. Testicular Volume (TV) was then estimated from the Testicular Width (TW), Length (L) and Height (H) using the Prolate Ellipsoid Formula (PEF) $L \times H \times W \times 0.52 \text{ cm}^3$, the images were displayed on grey scale and echogenicity.

RESULTS

The macroscopic assessment of semen prior to the semen analysis, visual assessment of the semen shows creamy or milky color that was consistently thick or thin in appearance, with the $7.1 \pm 00 \text{ pH}$ obtained for Red Sokoto goat buck in the current study. Other parameters, such as semen volume, progressive motility, concentration, live ratio, concentration and morphological abnormalities, are presented in Table 1.

For the study population, the mean standard deviation

Table 1: Semen characteristics of Red Sokoto buck goat in Sokoto.

Semen parameters	Mean \pm Standard deviation
Volume (ml)	0.85 \pm 0.299
Progressive motility (%)	77.33 \pm 14.305
Live ratio (%)	89.18 \pm 9.118
Morphology (%)	80.07 \pm 7.481
Concentration 10 ⁹ /ml	374 \pm 138.923
Color	Creamy/white
Consistency	Thick/thin
Ph	7.1 \pm 00

Table 2: Ultrasonographic biometrics parameters of Red Sokoto buck goat in Sokoto

Sonogram parameters	Mean \pm Standard deviation
LRT	7.80 \pm 0.706
HRT	6.67 \pm 0.666
WRT	4.21 \pm 0.406
VRT	115.23 \pm 25.264
LLT	7.36 \pm 0.576
HLT	6.39 \pm 0.648
WLT	3.66 \pm 0.453
VLT	89.95 \pm 18.280

LRT: Length of the right testicle, HRT: Height of the right testicle, WRT: Width of the right testicle, VRT: Volume of the right testicle, LLT: Length of the left testicle, HLT: Height of the left testicle, WLT; Width of the left testicle, VLT: Volume of the left testicle.

of the semen volume was 0.85 \pm 0.299 mls and the individual progressive motility were 77.33 \pm 14.305 %, Live spermatozoa 89.18 \pm 9.118 % with morphology of 80.07 \pm 7.481 % and the obtained semen concentration was 374 \pm 138.923 $\times 10^9$ spermatozoa / ml (table 1).

The testicles were well extended and pendulous prior to the sonogram biometrics measurements, and the testicular tissue appears as a hypo echoic region with scattered hyper echoic spots. The parameters measured for the sonogram includes; testicular volume, length, height and width (table 2). The mean standard deviation parameters for the sonogram biometrics are; length of the right testicles 7.80 \pm 0.706, height of the right testicles 6.67 \pm 0.666, width of the right testicles 4.21 \pm 0.406, volume of the right testicle 115.23 \pm 25.264, length of the left testicles 7.36 \pm 0.576, height of the left testicles 6.39 \pm 0.648, width of the left testicles 3.66 \pm 0.453 and the volume of the left testicles were 89.95 \pm 18.280 respectively (table 2).

DISCUSSION

Ensuring that male animals are reproductively sound is key to successful breeding, especially in indigenous breeds like the Red Sokoto buck. In this study, we combined semen analysis with ultrasound measurements of the testes to assess the fertility potential of Red

Sokoto bucks raised in Sokoto state, Nigeria.

The semen was consistently creamy or milky in color, varying in thickness, which is similar to the findings of Raji *et al.* (2016), for Red Sokoto bucks, and Oguejiofor *et al.* (2018) in West African dwarf goats. Such appearance is typical and indicates healthy semen quality. Variations in thickness could be influenced by factors such as hydration, nutrition, and overall health of the bucks (Evans, 2010).

The mean semen volume obtained in the present study was within normal range of 0.5 to 1.5 mL per ejaculate reported by Raji *et al.* (2016), for Red Sokoto bucks. Although it can be influenced by factors such as age, nutrition, health status and frequency of collection, Semen volume is a critical parameter as it influences the total number of spermatozoa available for fertilization Salamon & Maxwell, (1995), as well as the method used for semen collection (artificial vagina vs. electro-ejaculator). Bopape *et al.* (2015) reported that semen collection methods involving electro-ejaculator yielded higher semen volumes due to high levels of accessory gland secretions. Which is also the method used for this study. Adequate semen volume is essential for ensuring sufficient spermatozoa are available for fertilization. The mean Progressive motility was 77.33 \pm 14.305%. Which is closely similar to 0.607 \pm 0.22, 0.712 \pm 0.24, and 0.601 \pm 0.26, reported by Irkham *et al.*, (2017) in Red Sokoto Bucks. The mean value of 77.33% indicates a high level

of motility, suggesting good semen quality. High motility is a crucial indicator of fertility, reflecting the spermatozoa's ability to move efficiently towards the egg (Hafez & Hafez, 2000). Semen motility is a strong display of spermatozoa quality during semen evaluation that is why it is widely used in fertility laboratories as reported by Kulaksız *et al.* (2010). Research has shown that progressive motility above 70% is generally considered satisfactory for natural mating or artificial insemination (AI) in goats Kulaksız *et al.* (2010). Therefore, the obtained mean value suggests that the majority of bucks have semen suitable for reproductive purposes.

The percentage of live spermatozoa was $89.18 \pm 9.118\%$. This is similar to the report by Raji *et al.* (2012) in Red Sokoto Bucks, and Laku *et al.* (2021) in Sahel goat (84%). The obtained value is slightly higher than 87.5 ± 0.75 and 89.30 ± 2.10 reported by Olutunmogun *et al.* (2016) in Red Sokoto breed of goat in Nigeria. A high percentage of live spermatozoa (89.18%) suggest that most of the sperm cells are viable and capable of fertilization. The percentage of live spermatozoa is a vital indicator of semen quality. High viability shows a large proportion of sperm cells are alive and potentially capable of fertilizing an egg (Evans, 2010). This is a positive indicator of the reproductive health of the bucks. The standard deviation specifies some variability, which could be influenced by factors such as collection methods, handling, and individual health status as reported by Olutunmogun *et al.* (2016).

Morphologically normal spermatozoa accounted for $80.07 \pm 7.481\%$. This is similar to 70% to 90% reported by Raji *et al.* (2012) in Red Sokoto Bucks. Normal morphology is crucial for the sperm's ability to penetrate and fertilize the ovum. Abnormal sperm morphology can significantly impact fertility, so a high percentage of normal forms are beneficial (Oguejiofor *et al.*, 2018). A mean morphology value of 80.07% directs that the majority of sperm cells have a normal shape, which is conducive to high fertility rates. Studies have demonstrated that a morphology percentage above 70% is generally associated with good fertility outcomes in goats. Thus, the results for the Red Sokoto Bucks are within a favorable range Olutunmogun *et al.* (2016).

The semen concentration was $374 \pm 138.923 \times 10^9$ spermatozoa/mL, which is similar to 2 to 4 billion spermatozoa per mL as reported by Raji *et al.* (2012), Ubosi, *et al.* (1985), in Red Sokoto Bucks. The mean concentration of 374×10^9 spermatozoa/mL is quite high, demonstrating a robust sperm production capacity, high sperm concentration generally correlates with better fertility outcomes (Oguejiofor *et al.* 2018). This high concentration is advantageous for both natural mating and AI, as it ensures an adequate number of sperm cells for successful fertilization. The high standard deviation reflects significant variability, which could be due to individual differences in testicular function and health status. Semen concentration is a key factor in

determining the efficiency of AI and higher concentrations allow for more doses of semen to be prepared from a single ejaculate, increasing the productivity and efficiency of breeding programs, Laku *et al.* (2021).

The semen quality parameters obtained from this study of sixty Red Sokoto Bucks indicate generally good reproductive potential, with high progressive motility, live spermatozoa percentage, normal morphology, and semen concentration. These results will be favorable for both natural mating and AI, providing a solid foundation for effective breeding programs and reference value for Red Sokoto Bucks. The variability observed in the parameters shows the importance of regular semen quality assessment and selective breeding to optimize reproductive performance.

The determination of sonographic biometric parameters of the testicles, using the mobile ultrasound machine (iscan 2 multi made by Draminski): The testicular tissue appears as a hypo-echoic region with scattered hyper-echoic spots (Isoechoic) which were similar to those reported in matured West African dwarf buck goats by Ugwu (2009). We also observed that the testicular echotexture of the Red Sokoto bucks goats were similar to those reported in fertile bulls (Ali *et al.*, 2011), rams (Ulker *et al.*, 2005), camels (Pasha *et al.*, 2011) and Alpine goats (Carazo *et al.*, 2014). The echo texture and echogenicity of the vesicular gland and parenchyma in the present study were similar to those reported by Jucá *et al.* (2009) and Teixeira *et al.* (2013). This pattern is typical of healthy testicular tissue (Setchell, 1978). Although some authors have studied testicular echogenicity of healthy sheep (Amorim, 2010; Teixeira *et al.*, 2011; Andrade *et al.*, 2012; Urt, 2014), few have developed studies involving ultrasound biometry of the testicular parenchyma in red Sokoto goats, especially in sexually mature animals and correlated biometrics with all the variables presented in this study.

The Length of the right testicle was 7.80 ± 0.706 cm and that of left testicle was 7.36 ± 0.576 cm respectively. These are similar to the reports of Raji *et al.*; (2017), Oyeyemi (2012), and KaradağSarı, (2020) in Red Sokoto buck. The mean length of the right testicle is slightly longer than that of the left testicle. This unevenness is consistent with previous findings from manual measurements and is common in many livestock species. These are similar to the reports of Raji *et al.*; (2017), and in humans but with some variation in the values of these parameters, probably due to species variation Behre *et al.*, (1989), Kiridi *et al.*, 2012). However, reports on these testicular biometric parameters are scarce in Red Sokoto bucks. The greater length of the right testicle might be associated with its dominant role in spermatogenesis and hormonal production.

The height of the height testicle was 6.67 ± 0.666 cm, and that of the left testicle was 6.39 ± 0.648 cm. This is similar 5 to 7 cm range as reported by KaradağSarı, E., (2020) in Red Sokoto bucks. The right testicle also

exhibits a greater mean height compared to the left. This pattern reinforces the idea of functional asymmetry, where one testicle (often the right) tends to be larger and more active in terms of reproductive functions. This is similar to the finding of (Carazo, *et al* 2014). The standard deviations specify that height is a relatively stable trait among the sixty Red Sokoto bucks studied.

Width of the right testicle was 4.21 ± 0.406 cm and left testicle was 3.66 ± 0.453 cm respectively. This is also similar to an average range of 4 to 6 cm reported by Oyeyemi (2012). The width of the right testicle is higher than that of the left, which aligns with the observed differences in length and height. Heavier testicles are indicative of higher sperm production capabilities, as they contain more seminiferous tubules and Leydig cells, essential for spermatogenesis and testosterone production Saeed and Zaid (2018).

The Volume of the right Testicle was 115.23 ± 25.264 cm³ and that of the left testicle was 89.95 ± 18.280 cm³ respectively. Testicular volume is a critical parameter as it correlates with the total sperm output. The significantly larger volume of the right testicle suggests a higher sperm production capacity Mbaeri *et al.*, (2013). These volumetric measurements are more comprehensive indicators of testicular function compared to linear dimensions alone, as they account for the overall size and capacity of the testicles. Testicular volume has been documented to be an important index of spermatogenesis because about 98 % of the testis is made up of the seminiferous tubules where sperm cells are produced, Kollin *et al.*, (2006).

These findings for the first time suggest these as valuable source of animal protein thus offering a new, more accurate; none invasive method of evaluating testicular volume for Red Sokoto bucks which can be adopted to replace the invasive methods which require the removal of testes before testicular volume can be calculated, Franca *et al.*, (2000). The findings from sonographic measurements have practical applications in breeding programs. Bucks with larger testicular dimensions and volumes are likely to have better reproductive performance, making them ideal candidates for breeding, Saeed and Zaid (2018). Regular sonographic evaluations can help monitor the reproductive health of bucks, identifying any abnormalities or changes in testicular size that might affect fertility.

Early detection of issues can lead to timely interventions, Carazo *et al.*, (2014). The sonographic biometrics of Red Sokoto bucks revealed significant asymmetry between the right and left testicles, with the right testicle generally being larger in terms of length, height, width, and volume. These findings are consistent with the functional dominance of the right testicle observed in many livestock species, as reported by Memon, *et al.*, (2007). The use of ultrasonography provides a precise and non-invasive method for

evaluating reproductive potential, making it a valuable tool in breeding programs. By selecting bucks with superior testicular dimensions, breeders can enhance the fertility and productivity of their herds.

Correlation of the testicular sonographic biometric features and semen quality as tools in breeding soundness examination of red Sokoto goat (RSG) bucks

The evaluation of breeding soundness in male animals, particularly in indigenous breeds such as the Red Sokoto buck, is essential for successful reproductive performance. This study employed both semen analysis and ultrasonographic assessment of testicular biometric features to determine the reproductive soundness of Red Sokoto bucks in Sokoto, Nigeria. The results of semen quality revealed acceptable fertility parameters, including an average semen volume of 0.85 ± 0.299 ml, progressive motility of $77.33 \pm 14.305\%$, live spermatozoa of $89.18 \pm 9.118\%$, sperm morphology of $80.07 \pm 7.481\%$, and a sperm concentration of $374 \pm 138.923 \times 10^9$ spermatozoa/ml. Macroscopic semen characteristics showed creamy or milky coloration with consistency ranging from thick to thin and a pH of 7.1 ± 0.00 , indicating healthy seminal fluid conducive to sperm survival and mobility.

Ultrasonographic measurements of testicular dimensions showed mean values for the right testicle of 7.80 ± 0.706 cm in length, 6.67 ± 0.666 cm in height, 4.21 ± 0.406 cm in width, and a calculated volume of 115.23 ± 25.264 cm³. The left testicle measured slightly smaller, with a length of 7.36 ± 0.576 cm, height of 6.39 ± 0.648 cm, width of 3.66 ± 0.453 cm, and volume of 89.95 ± 18.280 cm³. The sonograms showed a uniform hypoechoic testicular parenchyma with dispersed hyperechoic spots, suggestive of active spermatogenic tissue.

The correlation between testicular biometric parameters and semen quality in this study indicates that larger testicular volumes, especially on the right testis, are associated with higher sperm concentrations. This finding is consistent with previous studies, such as those conducted by Raji *et al.* (2021), who reported a significant positive correlation between testicular volume and sperm production in both Red Sokoto and West African Dwarf bucks. Similarly, Souza *et al.* (2022) demonstrated that testicular width and volume, as measured by ultrasonography, serve as accurate predictors of semen output and fertility potential in goats.

Moreover, the echotexture of the testicular parenchyma has diagnostic significance. Uniform hypoechogenicity with fine hyperechoic stippling reflects normal seminiferous tubule integrity and active spermatogenesis, as observed in this study. Bello *et al.* (2020) emphasized that bucks with homogenous echotexture exhibited significantly better sperm motility and live-dead ratios

compared to those with heterogeneous parenchymal appearance. Rehman et al. (2023) also confirmed that the presence of testicular lesions or hyperechoic abnormalities correlates negatively with sperm morphology and motility.

It is noteworthy that slight asymmetry in testicular size, as noted between the right and left testes in the present study, is considered physiologically normal in goats. However, pronounced asymmetry may warrant further investigation, as suggested by Yusuf and Lawal (2023), who linked testicular uniformity to overall semen quality and fertility.

Therefore, combining ultrasonographic testicular evaluation with semen analysis provides a comprehensive approach to determining breeding soundness in Red Sokoto bucks. This integrated technique enhances the accuracy of selecting genetically and physiologically sound sires for breeding programs, which is especially important in regions where animal productivity is vital for livelihoods.

CONCLUSION

This study shows a strong association between testicular biometric parameters particularly testicular volume, and semen quality indicators in Red Sokoto bucks. The findings affirm that bucks with larger, uniformly echogenic testes tend to produce semen of higher quality, including better sperm concentration and motility. These results highlight the value of ultrasonography as a non-invasive, efficient, and reliable tool for assessing testicular health and predicting reproductive potential in breeding males.

Moreover, the echotexture of the testicular parenchyma provided essential diagnostic insights into spermatogenic activity. The observed correlations between testicular structure and semen attributes support the integration of both sonographic and seminal evaluations in comprehensive breeding soundness examinations.

This combined approach not only strengthens the selection of fertile sires for breeding programs but also contributes to improved genetic management and productivity in goat herds. Future studies with larger populations and longitudinal semen tracking are recommended to further validate these findings and expand their application in reproductive biotechnology for small ruminants.

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